

From Choreography Diagrams to Microservice Architecture Domain Models: Technical Report

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1. Introduction

This technical report is a companion of the following paper [7]:
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That paper contributes to the field of Microservices Architecture (MSA) [4]. In particular, it proposes a method to produce microservice domain models that minimises couplings among their business entities. A loose coupling among domain models is a recommended practice [5,6]. We have analysed code repositories of software projects following a MSA in order to investigate the problem and identify good practices regarding domain model complexity. This report provides some additional details about the code repository analysis that could not be included in the paper due to space constraints (see Section 0). Since the coupling among domain models often occurs at the business process design level and then propagates along the development life cycle, the method we propose requires modelling the business processes specifying the interactions among organisational units. We have chosen BPMN Choreography Diagrams [3] for such purposes. We propose to then specify the structure of the messages interchanged by the choreography participants, using the Message Structures [1] technique, borrowed from Communication Analysis [2]. We then propose a set of transformation guidelines to systematically derive the MSA domain models from the message structures. In the original paper [7], we detailed transformation guidelines in the form of pseudocode; in Section 3 we present them in a declarative form. In the original paper we have illustrated the application of the method with a single-case mechanism experiment [8]. However, space constraints prevented us from discussing the complete example. The reader can find the full example in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 concludes the report.

2. Analysis of code repositories of software projects following a MSA

Table 1. Extended analysis results of domain-driven microservice architecture code repositories.

Source	Alias	Branch	Languages	Dates Active	LOC	N° of Modules	Module Names	Max Aggregates	Max Nested Aggregates
https://github.com/dotnet-architecture/eShopOnContainers	eShopContainers	release/net-5	C#	04/09/2016 - 27/10/2021	176.8 kloc	5	Basket, Catalog, Identity, Ordering, Payment	1	1
https://github.com/idugalic/micro-company	micro-company	master	Java	27/03/2016 - 10/07/2020	127.1 kloc	4	Blog (Command Side), Project (Command Side), Blog (Query Side), Project (Query Side)/+ Common Blog, Common Project, Common	1	1
https://github.com/Microservice-API-Patterns/LakesideMutual	Lakeside Mutual	master	Java, Typescript	21/02/2021 - 19/04/2021	157.0 kloc	3	Customer Management, Customer Self Service, Policy	1	1
https://github.com/EdwinVW/pit-stop	Pit Stop	main	C#	24/09/2019 - 24/04/2023	97.4 kloc	5	Notification, Invoice, Customer Management (API?), Workshop Management (API?), Vehicle Management (API)	1	1
https://github.com/mspnp/microservices-reference-implementation	mspnp	main	C#	02/05/2021 - 06/07/2022	4.1 kloc	5	Delivery, Drone Scheduler, Ingestion*, Package, Workflow	4	2*
https://github.com/daxnet/we-text	WeText	master	C#	27/03/2016 - 15/11/2017	41.9 kloc	2	Accounts, Texting	1	1
https://github.com/microservices-patterns/ftgo-application	FTGO	1.0.0 RELEASE	Java	10/09/2017 - 29/09/2018	25.5 kloc	6	Accounting, Consumer, Delivery, Kitchen, Order, Restaurant	3	1
https://github.com/sivaprasreddy/spring-boot-microservices-series	sivalabs	master	Java	18/02/2018 - 16/04/2020	6.8 kloc	3	Catalog, Inventory, Order	1	1
https://github.com/ttulka/ddd-example-ecommerce-microservices	ttulka	main	Java	01/11/2020 - 06/03/2023	13.0 kloc	4	Billing, Sales (cart, catalog, order), Shipping (delivery, dispatching), Warehouse	1	1

3. Intention achievement guidelines for Microservice Domain Modelling through Message Structure Transformation

Table 2. Intention achievement guidelines for Microservice Domain Modelling through Message Structure Transformation

ID	Guideline Description
IAG 3.1	For each <i>BPMN.Participant</i> , create a <i>DDD.BoundedContext</i> package and keep a mapping between them.
IAG 3.2	Consider the <i>MS.MessageStructures</i> of all the <i>BPMN.Messages</i> received by a <i>BPMN.Participant</i> that is part of the organisation as input for generating the domain classes in the <i>DDD.BoundedContext</i> mapped from the <i>BPMN.Participant</i> .
IAG 3.3	For each <i>MS.MessageStructure</i> received by a <i>BPMN.Participant</i> , generate the domain classes from the <i>MS.Aggregation</i> within the first level (<i>MS.InitialAggregation</i>) as follows:
IAG 3.3.1	If the <i>MS.InitialAggregation</i> contains a <i>MS.DataField</i> marked as identifier and does not contain <i>MS.Aggregations</i> or <i>MS.ReferenceFields</i> , create a <i>DDD.Entity</i> . The <i>DDD.Entity</i> name follows the name of the <i>MS.Aggregation</i> and its attributes, the <i>MS.DataFields</i> of the <i>MS.Aggregation</i> .
IAG 3.3.2	If the <i>MS.InitialAggregation</i> contains a <i>MS.DataField</i> marked as identifier and contains nested <i>MS.Aggregations</i> or <i>MS.ReferenceFields</i> , create a <i>DDD.AggregateRoot</i> . The <i>DDD.AggregateRoot</i> name follows the name of the <i>MS.Aggregation</i> and its attributes, the <i>MS.DataFields</i> of the <i>MS.Aggregation</i> .
IAG 3.3.3	If the <i>MS.InitialAggregation</i> does not contain a <i>MS.DataField</i> field marked as identifier and does not contain nested <i>MS.Aggregations</i> and does not contain <i>MS.RreferenceFields</i> , create a <i>DDD.ValueObject</i> .
IAG 3.3.4	In any other case, <i>MS.InitialAggregation</i> does not create any domain classes, and the analysts must be warned about possible problems in the modelling of message structure.
IAG 3.4	For each <i>MS.ComplexStructure</i> and <i>MD.ReferenceField</i> contained in the <i>MS.InitialAggregation</i> , generate domain classes and the relationship with the domain classes generated in IAG 3.3 as follows:

IAG 3.4.1	If the contained element is a <i>MS.Aggregation</i> , create a domain class following the guidelines 3.4. Create a one-to-one composition association from the class generated by the <i>MS.InitialAggregation</i> to the created class.
IAG 3.4.2	If the contained element is a <i>MS.Iteration</i> , generate a domain class following the guidelines 3.4. Create a one-to-many composition association from the class generated by the <i>MS.InitialAggregation</i> to the created class.
IAG 3.4.3	If the contained element is a <i>MS.ReferenceField</i> that not extends an existing <i>MS.Aggregation</i> , create a one-to-one aggregation association from the class generated by the <i>MS.InitialAggregation</i> with the class generated by the <i>MS.Aggregation</i> referenced by the <i>MS.ReferenceField</i> .
IAG 3.4.4	If the contained element is a <i>MS.ReferenceField</i> that extends an existing <i>MS.Aggregation</i> , add the <i>MS.DataFields</i> as attributes for the class generated from the extended <i>MS.Aggregation</i> . Create a one-to-one composition association from the class generated by the <i>MS.InitialAggregation</i> with the class generated by the extended <i>MS.Aggregation</i> .
IAG 3.5	Generate domain classes for each nested <i>MS.Aggregations</i> , <i>MS.Iterations</i> , and <i>MS.ReferenceField</i> following the guidelines 3.4.1 to 3.4.4.
IAG 3.6	If after all the message structures are processed, a <i>DDD.Entity</i> class has not been associated to any <i>DDD.AggregateRoot</i> , the entity is considered as a <i>DDD.AggregateRoot</i> itself and stereotyped like that.
IAG 3.7	Modularise the bounded context: For each <i>DDD.AggregateRoot</i> not contained by other <i>DDD.AggregateRoots</i> , create a <i>DDD.Module</i> package within the <i>DDD.BoundedContext</i> of the <i>BPMN.Participant</i> under analysis, and move the <i>DDD.AggregateRoot</i> and its associated classes into the <i>DDD.Module</i> .

<pre> { SERVICE LINE = < Service ID + Service price > }+ TOTAL PRICE = < Total price > > </pre>			<pre> x t m o n e y d a t e d a t e m o n e y t e x t m o n e y m o n e y </pre>	<pre> maxico si01 2.00€ / day 462.00 € </pre>	
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Table 2. RATING message structure

FIELD	OBJECT	DOMAIN	EXAMPLE VALUE	
RATING = < Rating ID + Customer ID + Salesperson ID + Score + Comment +	g i i i i	d d r text text	numbe r text text	00056678 8857657-Z prat002 5 He was very helpful and responsive

Rating date >	i		number text date	25-05-2023
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Table 3. DELIVERY REQUEST message structure

FIELD	O	D	DOMAIN	EXAMPLE VALUE
DELIVERY = < Delivery number + Car owner ID + Customer ID + Delivery address + Delivery comments + Pick-up date + Return date >	g	i	number text text text text date date	665364787 7675535-F 8857657-Z Av. Blue Molar 334, 3683CD, Cumbia Difficult to park in that area 15-08-2023 31-08-2023

Table 4. DELIVERY CONFIRMATION message structure

FIELD	O	E	DOMAIN	EXAMPLE VALUE
DELIVERY CONFIRMATION = < Delivery + Delivery confirmation + Reception comments + >	i	e	Delivery boolean text	665364787 True The car has a scratch in the left front door

Fig. 2. Figure 2. Domain model resulting from the application of the transformation guidelines to the choreography task CLOSE RENTAL DEAL (i.e. message structure RENTAL).

Fig. 3. Figure 3. Domain model resulting from the application of the transformation guidelines to the choreography task RATE SALESPERSON (i.e. message structure RATING).

Fig. 4. Figure 4. Domain model resulting from the application of the transformation guidelines to the choreography tasks REQUEST CAR DELIVERY and CONFIRM DELIVERY (i.e. message structures DELIVERY REQUEST and DELIVERY CONFIRMATION).

5. Conclusions

This report complements a paper contributing a method to model business processes in the context of Microservices Architecture and systematically deriving the domain models of the microservices [7]. We have presented information that could not be included in the original paper for reasons of space. As future work, we intend to refine the guidelines, validate them through expert assessment, and implement the transformation guidelines with a model-to-model transformation language. We look forward to collaborating with the industrial community of MSA developers in this research endeavour.

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